

Survival of 9 rice varieties in 2 types of containers submerged for 7 days at seedling stage. IRRI, 1980.

Variety	Mean percentage of survival	
	Vial	Square pot
Thavalu 15314	100	100
Thavalu 15325	100	100
Kurkaruppan	100	96
FR13A	100	90
KDML105	50	40
SML Temerin	38	23
IR8	38	80
IR42	50	16
IR38	17	30
Mean	66	64

“t” calculated value = 0.2927 ns at df. 8.

square pots may be necessary.

The study shows that screening for submergence tolerance at seedling stage during RGA is possible. Elimination of most of the susceptible lines will decrease the RGA population and increase the chances of the remaining lines to survive submergence under field conditions. ■

Selection for earliness or short growth duration during rapid generation advance in rice breeding

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Delayed heading or long growth duration is a major effect of low temperature on rice plants. When temperature is low, delayed panicle initiation, which may result from long growth duration, causes degeneration of spikelets and sterility. Flowering of rice plants in low temperatures causes sterility.

A 130-day cultivar in the tropics may have a growth duration of 200 days in low-temperature areas. To have a duration of 130-150 days in those areas, it should mature only within 90-100 days in the lowland tropics. Earliness is therefore one of the main criteria used for selection in improving cultivars for the low-temperature areas.

In an experiment to determine if selection for earliness is possible during the rapid generation advance (RGA) and in what generation it is feasible, the seeds

of two crosses — IR20654 (K78-13/IR5908-125-1) and IR22553 (Fujisaka 5/Knl B-361-8-6-9) — were sown in plastic pots (5.2 cm diam × 5.0 cm high) filled with soil and added fertilizer. Flowering dates for both F₂ and F₃ plants were noted.

Selection of F₂ plants that flowered in 70 days or less resulted in a 31% reduction of the population for IR22553 and 12% for IR20654. The reduction in population greatly facilitated the handling of the materials and provided space for more plants. However, in the IR22553 cross, 28% of the short-growth-duration lines (< 70 days) in the F₃ were eliminated when selection for earliness was made in F₂ plants. Similarly, 15% in

IR20654 were lost. In a large F₂ population, an average loss of 21% may be permissible.

Of the F₃ population that resulted from selection for earliness in F₂ of the cross IR22553 (< 70 days), 72% had a growth duration of less than 70 days. The value for IR20654 was 84%. These high values justify early selection (at F₂) for earliness (see table).

Selection for earliness, however, does not involve cold tolerance at seedling stage. If selection for earliness is made at F₂, a population of around 2,000 plants should be the minimum so that F₃ selection for cold tolerance at seedling stage could be conducted. ■

Heading days of 2 crosses in 2 generations under rapid generation advance.

F ₃	IR22553 F ₂ plants (no.)		F ₃	IR20654 F ₂ plants (no.)	
	51-70 d	71-90 d		51-70 d	71-108 d
41-70d	316	120	51-70 d	623	111
71-100 d	21	28	71-80 d	114	51

Problems and prospects of rice in Manipur

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Rice is the principal crop of the State of Manipur in the northeast corner of India. The State comprises an area of 22,356 km² and lies between 23.50° and 25.41° N latitude and 93° and 94.45° E longitude. The State is hilly and undulating except for the valley portion of about 2,235 km². The elevation of the valley is about 765-890 m; in the hills, the altitude ranges from 900 to 3,010 m. The climate is subtropical with assured rainfall, but temperature and other meteorologic conditions vary. Maximum temperatures of about 32° C in the valley and 27° C in the hills are registered in June-July. Minimum temperatures of about 1.5° C in the plains to 0° C in the hills are registered in December-January. Average annual rainfall varies from 1,350 mm in the valley to 1,800 mm in the

hills. The dry season from December to March has little rainfall.

An area of 172,000 ha under rice cultivation yields an average of 1.5 t/ha. In the valley rice, mostly transplanted, is grown in low-lying areas. Rice is also the main crop in the hills. Farmers in the north and northeast practice terraced cultivation. Transplanting normally is from mid-June to late July. Harvest is from late October to late November. All these operations are 15 to 20 days early in the hills. More than 80% of the area is planted to local glutinous varieties such as Moirangphou, Phoudum, Kakchingphou, and Langmanbi — preferred by the local population.

Over the last decade the Department of Agriculture has had limited success in introducing some high-yielding, short-duration, photoperiod-insensitive varieties such as IR8, Jaya, Ratna, and Palaman. IR24 is becoming popular because of its high yield and low amylose character, but it is very susceptible to blast, a disease that is favored by weather conditions in Manipur. With the development of